

Finding the gap

Addressing the international migration data gaps

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KEY FINDINGS

- The main shortcomings in international migration data include differences in definitions and measurement, neglecting drivers or reasons for migration, under-coverage of certain geographical regions in the sources, demographic specificities of migrants, and time lag in the release of data for policymakers.
- Relatively more data exist on conventions-based international migrants, students, migrant stocks, remittances, and human trafficking and fewer data are gathered on irregular migration, migrants' health, migration policies, recruitment costs, return migration, smuggling, integration, missing population groups and migration flows.
- The quality and availability of data vary across regions and countries. More developed countries collect relatively accurate statistics with more variables than economically challenged countries.
- Policymakers receive data after a significant delay and of insufficient quality, or at an inadequate disaggregation level.
- A deeper understanding of the root causes and drivers of migration and of their interrelations with people's propensity to migrate is needed. Projections and scenarios based on this are essential for appropriate planning and effective policymaking.
- Although quantitative data are considered as the main resource for evidence-based policymaking, qualitative data are just as crucial.
- Given the gender-specific nature of migration, a deficient gender dimension in current data clouds the analysis of the intersections between migration and gender.
- Understanding how gender shapes migrants' needs and decision-making processes is critical for both research, policy and humanitarian purposes.
- Alternative data sources and novel methodologies can serve to collect hard-to-find data and complement the available information; however, these approaches should be assessed with great care considering the ethical and human rights aspects.
- Countries are expected to improve their capacity to generate timely, reliable, and comparable data on migration, in order to help guide policymakers in devising evidence-based policies and plans of action to tackle migration aspects of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG).

ABSTRACT

Gaps in international migration data have persisted ever since the international organisations started gathering and presenting data on migration. These data gaps hinder policymakers in their development of efficient policies for better migration management. This policy brief presents the most common and persistent gaps within the international migration data portals and recommends relevant solutions. The gaps encompass inconsistencies in definitions and measures, neglecting the drivers of migration, under-coverage of major geographies and demographic specificities of migrants, and a lag in timely representation of the data. Moreover, the policy brief discusses the possibilities of tackling the data challenges through alternative data sources and methodologies such as Big Data analytics.

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Migration has an indispensable spot on social and political agendas around the world. In Europe, discussions around migration have peaked since 2015. Public and policy debates have also focussed on the phenomenon of migration during the COVID-19 pandemic, especially in light of the exacerbating intersectional issues of labour rights, citizenship, ethnicity and health inequalities. Despite the large number of official statistics in the EU member states, only a part of the complexity of the migration phenomena can be captured through data. The EU is in a better position in terms of migration data than many other world regions. Nevertheless, the recent migration crisis in Europe brought about a number of national action plans, including measures to increase the adequacy of the data to address policy needs. Numerous international actions arose as well, such as the [Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration](#), which recognises, as one of its objectives, the need to collect and utilise accurate data as a basis for evidence-informed policymaking. The global-level migration indicators are relatively under-developed; hence, countries are expected to improve the capacity to generate **timely, reliable, and comparable data on migration** to help guide policy makers devise evidence-based policies and plans of action to tackle migration aspects of the SDGs.

Given the advocacy for evidence-based or data-driven policymaking, **what constitutes ‘evidence’** has great importance. For policymakers, it is essential to work with appropriate data on migration during all phases of the policy cycle and it is crucial to strengthen international migration statistics to better inform the public debate and to address migration challenges effectively. In recent years there have been significant improvements in the availability and use of migration data. Nevertheless, gaps persist. In order to draw more accurate predictive scenarios, it is crucial to have an accurate understanding of data gaps. Therefore, it is essential to improve statistical resources that reflect the dynamics of migration, the various intersections of drivers, hybrid identities, economics, globalisation and gender accurately. Ongoing efforts to harmonise definitions and new data sources have contributed to the availability and quality of information on migratory flows. However, coherence, consistency and comparability in national and international migration statistics may still be the exception rather than the standard.

Gaps in international data

Adequate data is key to evidence-informed policymaking. Although considerable amounts of data on migration have been collected by several countries, there are no mecha-

nisms to centralize, disaggregate and cross-reference all data collected from various branches of the government. The main purpose of most of these data is to answer local/national situations. Data collection methodology is therefore often tailored to local circumstances, which restricts data comparability across countries.

While there is a consensus among experts that the main challenges within the existing data are **differences and inconsistencies in the definitions and measures** in the main international migration statistics databases, including those mentioned above, there are other gaps which are equally important to be addressed for drawing accurate policies. These pertain to neglecting focus on the **drivers or reasons for migration, geography covered in the data sources, demographic specificities** of migrants, and **a lag in timely** release of data for the public and researchers.

Definitions and measurements

In recent decades, international organisations which present international migration data have repeatedly flagged the challenge of inconsistent definitions and measures. The EU regulation was to a high extent efficient in improving data within the EU, but there are still major inconsistencies in definitions of data coming from different EU member states as they use different sources for collecting data. Moreover, migration being a multidimensional phenomenon across the globe, it is not sufficient to have high quality data for only one region or certain blocks of countries. The efforts by international organisations to resolve the issues related to definition and measurement have not been particularly efficient, especially among non-EU countries, as statistical information largely pertains to the responsibilities of national governments and many countries without legal commitments do not prioritise having high quality data on migration. While the expectations from international organisations to improve the definition issues are high, in reality it is up to national governments to adapt to the definitions that are recommended by the United Nations.

Drivers for migration

Although the drivers for migration are important factors for policymaking, the reasons for migration are most often not covered in the international migration data sources, mostly due to a high level of aggregation. In the existing data collection systems, the registration categories define the focus, and the groups of interest are refugees and asylum seekers, work-based migrants, students, and to

some extent irregular migrants¹. All other factors behind migration are not adequately included in the data systems. Moreover, the data-sources do not always cover the reasons for departure as well as return. That is to say, the current migration databases are collecting data based on past migration assumptions and flows, while the current data do not allow to understand what shapes international migration.

Drivers and policy nexus

When discussing what drives migration, it is essential to keep in mind that migration decisions and outcomes can be shaped overtly or inadvertently by policies. Hence, it is crucial to understand how policies (relating to migration, foreign affairs, integration, labour market and development) interact with drivers in a myriad of ways to sustain, limit or perpetuate migration. Models that hinge on economic drivers for migration often do not address the sociocultural context, the complexity of social behaviour and individual choice in decision making. In addition to qualitative data, alternative data sources and novel methodologies can serve to collect hard-to-find data and complement the available knowledge. Therefore, although quantitative data is considered as the main source of evidence-based policymaking, qualitative data is just as crucial.

Geographical coverage

There is a large imbalance in the data collection, the quality and availability of data across regions. Rich and more developed countries are able to collect high quality data, some national governments are even obliged by law, while others (especially developing countries) are financially constrained, or migration data is not in their priorities. Although most migrations take place in developing countries and regions, the data are scarce for those regions. A consistent challenge for almost all countries is that migrants who have already moved to another host country are counted differently in the receiving countries. Moreover, there are different assumptions and attributes to the regions ascribed in different local contexts. For instance, in Belgium the term ‘Maghrebians migrants’ may refer to Moroccans, while in France it would indicate Algerians. Likewise, Latin Americans could be seen differently in Belgium and Portugal. Thus, the same data could also refer to very different realities.

Demography and hidden populations

Many demographic characteristics of migrants such as education, gender, administrative status, types and duration of movements are, to a large extent, not covered in the international migration databases. Demographic data on migrants should be disaggregated in terms of multiple variables – gender, language, skill, ethnicity, age. This will allow to better understand the heterogeneity within and similarities among different migrant categories. The available datasets neglect, to a large extent, the demographic characteristics of global migrants. The missing demographic information includes details on irregular migrants, information on visa, intra EU mobility, travellers and other disadvantaged groups in the databases.² These categories are often referred to as hidden populations or undefined mobility. Hidden groups that are not included in the statistics include travellers, Roma people, intra EU migrants, even the homeless and so forth. In many datasets, asylum seekers are included only once they have been granted refugee status and received a temporary or permanent residence permit while in some other instances, they are registered at an earlier stage of the asylum process and the status often does not change in official statistics despite receiving an approval or rejection decision. There is a dire need to improve the inclusiveness of the data sources by adding the missing population and more demographic characteristics of such people.

Gender gaps in migration data: a festering sore

Although female migrants make up half of the global migrant population, there has been very little coordinated effort to incorporate gender into international migration scholarship. A lack of adequate gender-based migration policies perpetuate inequalities and discrimination that female migrants face at different stages of the migration process. Gender is still measured by “sex” in official statistics and collection of reliable and accurate sex-disaggregated data is crucial to address information gaps and present a more holistic analysis of the experiences of migrant women. It will also help analysts and experts identify types and patterns of female migration, and factors at individual, familial and societal levels affecting unique experiences of women at all stages of the migration process. Despite available aggregate level data, a lack of reliable sex-disaggregated data leads to overlooking women-specific needs and health problems and leaves migrant and refugee women and girls in danger and without access

1 The European Border and Coast Guard Agency, also known as Frontex, presents data on irregular border crossings in Europe on a monthly basis. See here: <https://frontex.europa.eu/along-eu-borders/migratory-map/>

2 See Fassmann et al. (2009)

to basic services. Data on gender are not available for irregular and undocumented migration, involving an extra layer of vulnerability. The lacking gender dimension in prevailing data convolutes inference and discourse at the intersection of migration and gender. Better statistics and better response can only be designed through inclusive and gender-sensitive policies.

Timeliness

Another very important challenge with migration data is the availability of data at the appropriate time. At the beginning of 2021, the most recent international migration data from UN DESA is for 2019, from OECD for 2016, from IOM for 2020, and from Eurostat for 2018. The publication of migration statistics usually takes place with a considerable delay and it varies by region and data source. The data are collected under different definitions, e.g., long term, short term, and combining that data under a unified definition makes the process longer for projections of international migration. Certain issues about timeliness are directly related to the harmonisation of data on internal migration. Gathering and publishing data that are collected at lower levels is a very time-consuming process, and the periodicity differs in each country. Projecting these data in a single harmonised dataset on international migration significantly decreases their quality. Even data collected directly by the UN or EU agencies are made available with significant time lag. Problematic access to timely data is not only emphasised in academic work: the UN, European Commission and other international organisations have also stressed its importance.

Can new approaches solve the data challenges?

Big data and new methodologies for migration statistics

The limitations of existing migration data hinder the accuracy of predictive scenarios. These limitations relate to timing issues, quality of data, insufficient clarification of the definitions, and disaggregation level of some variables. Moreover, the data fail to catch up with the contemporary migration dynamics, such as forced migration due to the conflicts and environmental threats. Accordingly, a more comprehensive approach is needed. The challenge can be addressed by improving the existing datasets through the exploitation of new data sources. Although there is a novel list of potential data sources that could provide valuable, real-time insights, these remain largely underused for the time being.

International organisations have invested notable efforts in tackling data challenges through alternative data

sources and methodologies such as Big Data analytics. The Global Migration Data Analysis Centre (GMDAC) was established in 2015 by the IOM and hosts the 'Migration Data Portal' which aims at gathering the data that are scattered across different organisations and agencies. On the other hand, the EC's Knowledge Centre on Migration and Demography (KCMD), established on 20 June 2016, aims to provide scientific evidence for EU policymaking tailored to the needs of Commission services and the European External Action Service (EEAS). With the aim of harnessing data innovation for migration analysis and policymaking while ensuring the ethical use of data and the protection of individuals' privacy, these two organisations (GMDAC and KCMD) convene the Big Data for Migration Alliance (BD4M). The most recent and valuable initiatives of the BD4M are the New Data Innovation Directory and the 100 Questions Initiative.

These initiatives mainly focus on the use of Big Data for migration estimates such as population movements (migration flows and stocks) and to study cultural aspects related to acceptance and integration of migrants. Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications around the world and in Europe address varied features of migration management such as processing administration and stocks and managing migration through border security. Furthermore, ethical and human rights aspects initiate salient discussions over the lack of regulations for automated decision-making in visa and asylum applications and AI lie detectors for immigrants and refugees. In short, the potential of Big Data and AI analytics is remarkable, yet there is an urgent need for ethically responsible and privacy-safeguarding regulations and frameworks.

Europe's New (com)Pact for Migration and Asylum

On 23 September 2020, the European Commission presented the New Pact on Migration and Asylum, which aims for more 'effective' border controls in the Schengen region, better procedures and information sharing and solidarity among and within EU member countries and more nuanced migration and integration policies. The pact is stressing the need of a policy monitoring system.

Particularly noteworthy is the emphasis of the pact on updating the Eurodac database and on better information sharing among countries, especially, from border regions. As per this, biometric data including fingerprints will be collected from asylum seekers and migrants. This has already been flagged by civil society organisations as a move that will increase the risk of people being victimised and persecuted. As per the revised Eurodac proposal, personal data (age, date of birth, facial image, identity docu-

ments and nationality) will be stored in a way immediately accessible by all member states. There is a lower minimum age for the collection of fingerprints, which can now start at age 6. It will also be up to member states to see and compare whether a person entered legally or illegally, crossed borders or previously applied for asylum. The New Pact touts this as a critical step towards strengthening the external border of the European Union and limiting the internal movement of asylum seekers. 'The external border is where the EU needs to close the gaps between external border controls and return procedures.' These measures are also meant to counter the possibility of an asylum request being used as an access point to the EU. They also facilitate the access of law enforcement authorities through alphanumeric sequences.

Another critical aspect of this dimension is the 'accelerated decision mechanism'. The Pact is looking into procedures that will allow asylum requests to be processed faster and people forced to return immediately in the case of rejection. Until the screening procedure is completed, the person will not be considered as having legally entered the state's territory, leading to a stronger link between asylum and expulsion. Given the increasing emphasis on data collection by security and border agencies, there is a need for a detailed data protection impact assessment and introduction of appropriate and effective safeguards. The Pact should ensure full respect to the fundamental rights of persons who seek international protection and other migrants, including their right to data protection and privacy.

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